

Literature Review on the Use of Global Fuzzy Numbers in Occupational Health and Safety Risk Assessment Processes

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Abstract

Occupational health and safety (OHS) is a critical component of workplace management aimed at protecting employees and preventing accidents and occupational diseases. Traditional risk assessment methods, such as the 5×5 Matrix, Fine-Kinney, and Failure Mode and Effects Analysis, often face limitations in capturing uncertainty and expert hesitation. To address these challenges, fuzzy logic-based approaches, particularly Spherical Fuzzy Sets (SFSs), have been introduced. SFSs allow decision-makers to independently define membership, non-membership, and hesitancy degrees, providing a more comprehensive representation of uncertainty in risk assessment processes. This study reviews the theoretical foundations of OHS, risk assessment methods, fuzzy logic, and SFSs, highlighting their integration in occupational risk management. The findings suggest that SFS-based hybrid models can significantly improve decision-making in OHS by accommodating subjective judgments and multidimensional risk factors.

Keywords: Risk Assessment, Fuzzy Logic, Spherical Fuzzy Sets, Occupational health and Safety

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Introduction

Occupational health and safety (OHS) is a process that has emerged as one of the most essential systems since the inception of working life. It has been regulated in different ways in legislation due to varying work environments and employee profiles around the world. These systems are regulated by law, integrated into the business environment, and implemented in the workplace with the guidance of OHS professionals, who are the primary implementers of the systems. To ensure the effectiveness of all users and the environment in terms of OHS, particularly worker and workplace safety, this system must be implemented in a manner that is as stable and continuous as possible. In OHS practices, identifying and controlling the risks to which workers are exposed is of great importance. In this context, risk analysis and risk assessment studies are among the most comprehensive activities carried out in workplaces [1]. By their very nature, businesses harbor multiple hazards and risks, bringing with them various risks of harm to employees and those in the surrounding area. Therefore, taking proactive measures based on risk analysis is a critical necessity.

Risk assessment studies are a systematic process aimed at identifying, analyzing, and evaluating potential risks and their impact on an organization, project, or activity. Risk assessment involves evaluating both the likelihood of a risk occurring and the potential severity of its impact (Özkılıç, 2003). The purpose of risk assessment is to provide valuable information that can help decision-makers effectively understand and manage risks. Today, different risk assessment methods are used in various sectors. Among the most commonly used risk assessment methods in the field of occupational health and safety are the 5*5 Matrix method, the Fine-Kinney method, and the Failure Mode and Effects Analysis method (Yakut & Kaya, 2025).

Fuzzy logic-based risk assessment models have been developed to make risk assessments more objective today. The integration of fuzzy sets within the scope of fuzzy logic allows for a more comprehensive analysis and assessment of risks. Multiple fuzzy numbers based on fuzzy sets and fuzzy logic are used in the literature. Spherical Fuzzy Numbers (SFN) are at the forefront these. Spherical Fuzzy Numbers were developed and introduced to the literature by Kutlu Gundogdu and Kahraman (2019). These fuzzy numbers, which evaluate within a reliable comprehensive range, enable decision-makers to obtain reliable results.

Occupational Health and Safety

Occupational health and safety encompasses all scientific studies conducted with the aim of improving health and safety conditions in workplaces. The primary objective of this system is to protect employees and take appropriate measures accordingly. These studies, conducted with the goal of taking proactive measures, prioritize preventing workplace accidents and occupational diseases that may arise in workplaces and under the conditions of work.

Occupational Health and Safety (OHS), a set of rules with widespread application around the world and corresponding legal obligations, has different implementation conditions in each country. For this reason, there are also differences in its application. Although all applications differ, they are fundamentally focused on the common goal of protecting employees. The OHS system is based on a risk management approach that is sustainable in both technical

and managerial dimensions. Today, OHS management systems are based on approaches that adopt a risk-based mindset and embrace a continuous improvement cycle. OHS is considered not only a legal obligation but also a strategic management area in terms of sustainable production, corporate reputation, and organizational performance (ISO, 2018).

Risk Assessment Methods

The increasing industrialization, automation, and technological integration have made production processes more complex; this has led to a diversification in the types of hazards emerging in the workplace, both in terms of quantity and quality. This increased complexity has brought not only technical risks to the fore, but also organizational and managerial risk factors, thereby raising societal expectations regarding acceptable risk levels to a more sensitive level. In this context, risk analysis and risk assessment practices stand out as a fundamental tool in preventing occupational accidents and diseases, requiring businesses to identify and control hazards in advance.

OHS risk assessment is considered a comprehensive and dynamic management process that involves identifying potential hazards, analyzing risks in terms of probability and severity, and planning and implementing appropriate control measures (Tixier et al., 2002). In the context of occupational health and safety, various risk assessment methods have been developed to identify hazards in the workplace, analyze the risks arising from these hazards, and take effective measures.

The selection of these methods may vary depending on variables such as the characteristics of the workplace, the types of hazards, and the available resources (Simsek, 2020). Risk assessment methods are systematic approaches used in occupational health and safety and general risk management to identify potential hazards, analyze the consequences these hazards may cause, and rank risks according to their level of importance.

These methods are considered fundamental tools for effectively understanding and controlling uncertainties. In the assessment process, considering the likelihood of risks occurring alongside their potential effects enables more accurate decision-making (Medeni & İlhan, 2024). Risk assessment methods used in occupational health and safety vary according to their scope of application and level of analysis.

Some methods focus on predicting potential technical failures and system errors by examining production systems, machinery, and process designs, while others focus on assessing the physical, chemical, biological, and ergonomic hazards to which workers are exposed. In this context, the structural characteristics of the system being evaluated, the source of the hazards, and the unique dynamics of the sector directly influence the nature of the method to be used; this situation also necessitates the development of risk assessment models specific to different industries (Zorluer & Eleren, 2011).

Fuzzy Logic

Fuzzy logic is a mathematical theory first established in 1961 by Azerbaijani mathematician Lotfi A. Zadeh (Zadeh,1965). In his work published in 1965, Zadeh developed fuzzy logic and fuzzy set theory to model uncertain, complex systems where classical logic falls short, thereby contributing to the literature. This approach is notable for its ability to mimic human reasoning and intuition (Zadeh,1975).

According to Zadeh, the fundamental purpose of fuzzy logic is to model two important cognitive abilities of humans. The first is the ability to reason, communicate, and make logical decisions based on information that is uncertain, incomplete, or inconsistent. The second is the ability to perform various physical and mental tasks without the need for any measurement or mathematical calculation .

Fuzzy logic is based on the way humans interpret the information they acquire through their life experiences, shaped by environmental influences, and their developing senses. Throughout their lives, humans assign various values and meanings to their environment. As experience increases during this process, the clear boundaries in the perception of reality gradually become blurred .

Unlike fuzzy logic, propositions in the classical logic system can only take two values. These values are true (1) and false (0). Fuzzy logic, which operates on a different scale, argues that truth is not limited to these two boundary values, but rather can be expressed as a graded truth function capable of taking an infinite number of values between 0 and 1(Zadeh,1975). This approach plays an important role in modeling the uncertainties and complex thought processes of real life in a more flexible manner .

Types of Fuzzy Sets

Fuzzy set theory offers a flexible structure that enables the mathematical modeling of uncertainty and ambiguity, providing an important alternative in complex decision-making environments where classical binary logic systems fall short.

First introduced by Lotfi A. Zadeh, fuzzy sets define the degree of membership of elements in a set within the range $[0,1]$, based on the concept of graded membership rather than precise boundaries (Zadeh, 1965). Over time, the increasing complexity of decision-making problems and the need to better represent the multidimensional structure of uncertainty led to the development of different types of fuzzy sets, such as intuitionistic fuzzy sets, type-2 fuzzy sets, Pythagorean fuzzy sets, and global fuzzy sets. This diversity provides more flexible and realistic modeling capabilities, particularly in risk analysis, multi-criteria decision-making, and engineering applications.

Fuzzy Set Types and Researchers

	 Researcher(s)	
1965	Fuzzy Sets	L.A. Zadeh
1975	Type-2 Fuzzy Sets	L.A. Zadeh
1983	Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets	K. Atanassov
2006	Neutrosophic Sets	F. Smarandache
2010	Uncertain Fuzzy Sets	V. Torra
2013	Pythagorean Fuzzy Sets	R.R. Yager
2013	Picture Fuzzy Sets	B.H. Cuong & V. Kreinovich
2016	Q-Rung Orthopair Fuzzy Sets	R.R. Yager
2019	Spherical Fuzzy Sets	F. Kutlu Gundogdu & C. Kahraman
2019	Fermat Fuzzy Sets	M. Senapati & R.R. Yager

Source:(Kutlu Gundogdu&Kahraman,2019)

Spherical Fuzzy Sets

Spherical fuzzy sets were introduced into the literature by Kutlu Gundogdu and Kahraman (Kutlu Gundogdu & Kahraman,2019) as an extension of fuzzy sets. According to this development model, the logic underlying SFS is that decision makers define a membership function on a global surface by generalizing the extensions of other fuzzy sets .

This allows them to independently assign the parameters of the function defined on the spherical fuzzy surface to a wider domain . SFS, which integrate the concepts of Pythagorean fuzzy numbers and Neutrosophic fuzzy numbers, are focused on enabling decision makers to extend traditional fuzzy sets by representing membership functions on a spherical surface and independently adjusting the parameters of these functions over a wider domain. They are based on obtaining highly reliable results in fuzzy sets(Kutlu Gundogdu & Kahraman,2019) .

To address these constraints, Gündoğdu and Kahraman (2019a) introduced Spherical Fuzzy Sets (SFS). SFS allows decision makers to define a membership degree (μ), a non-membership degree (ν), and a hesitancy degree (π) independently, provided that the sum of their squares falls within the unit sphere:

This geometric flexibility provides a larger preference volume compared to other fuzzy extensions, making it a superior tool for capturing human subjectivity in complex scenarios.

Table 1 shows the linguistic and spherical values of SFSs.

$$\tilde{A}_S = \{ \langle x, \mu_{\tilde{A}_S}(x), \nu_{\tilde{A}_S}(x), \pi_{\tilde{A}_S}(x) | x \in X \rangle \} \quad (1)$$

$$0 \leq \mu_{\tilde{A}_S}^2(x) + \nu_{\tilde{A}_S}^2(x) + \pi_{\tilde{A}_S}^2(x) \leq 1, \forall x \in X \quad (2)$$

Tablo 1. Küresel bulanık sayılar ve dilsel değişkenler [46,47]

Linguistic variables	(μ, ν, η)	Sayı değerleri
Absolutely More Importance (AMI)	(0.9,0.1,0.1)	9
Very High Importance(VHI)	(0.8,0.2,0.2)	7
High Importance (HI)	(0.7,0.3,0.3)	5
Slightly More Importance(SMI)	(0.6,0.4,0.4)	3
Equally Importance(EI)	(0.5,0.5,0.5)	1
Slightly Low Imporance(SLI)	(0.4,0.6,0.4)	1/3
Low Importance(LI)	(0.3,0.7,0.3)	1/5
Very Low Importance(VLI)	(0.2,0.8,0.2)	1/7
Absolutely Low Importance (ALI)	(0.1,0.9,0.1)	1/9

Source:(Kutlu Gundogdu&Kahraman,2019)

The Use of Spherical Fuzzy Sets in OHS Risk Assessment Processes

Since their introduction into the literature, SFSs have been used for various purposes in a wide range of fields. These numbers have made it easier for decision-makers to establish a reliable connection between criteria and alternatives and obtain reliable results.

One of the primary areas where SFSs are widely used is risk assessment processes in the field of occupational safety and health (OHS). These numbers facilitate the analysis of hazards and the assessment of risks in reliable ranges and dimensions for OSH professionals in the field.

Integration with different risk assessment models is possible, and SFSs can be used.

OHS risk assessment involves identifying hazards and rating them according to criteria such as probability, severity, and sometimes detectability. Traditional methods cannot fully reflect the

uncertainty (indecision or impartiality) in expert opinions. SFSs fill this gap by allowing decision-makers to independently define membership, non-membership, and hesitation levels. The following section shows risk assessment studies where SFSs have been used in different fields recently.

Gündoğdu and Seyfi-Shishavan (2021) developed a two-stage model using SFS to analyze complex OHS risks encountered in shipyards. In this study, criterion weights were determined using SF-AHP (Spherical Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process), and risks were prioritized using the SF-VIKOR method. The results of the study showed that the method is more accurate than traditional methods in identifying high-risk hazards.

Yılmaz Kaya and Lotfi (2022) used SFS and the SAW (Simple Aggregate Weighting) method in their study on inventory management aimed at reducing OSH risks. This study demonstrated how OHS risks can be integrated with SFS not only in operational processes but also in supply chain processes.

In a study on ergonomic risks, a critical subfield of occupational safety and health, the SF-AHP and Fuzzy CoCoSo methods were integrated to examine the hazards in shipyard floating dock operations (Kutlu Gundogdu, 2024).

In high-risk sectors such as manufacturing and the paint industry, Hacibektasoglu et al. (2021) prioritized hazards in the paint industry using an SFS-based hybrid risk analysis method.

The link between sustainability and operational OHS management has been examined by Kutlu Gundogdu (2024) through shipyard floating dock operations. In this study, criteria were weighted using SF-AHP, while alternative risk scenarios were ranked using the Fuzzy CoCoSo method.

Furthermore, Wen et al. (2023) developed a new perspective on risk ranking problems by combining the objective weights of risk factors with SFS.

Wang et al. (2024) presented a model that more effectively evaluates uncertain risk data by integrating the Fine–Kinney method with SFNs and the Choquet integral in their study.

Bayhun and Demirel (2024) presented a model that combines the Fine–Kinney method with global fuzzy AHP and SF- CoCoSo (Combined Compromise Solution) methods to assess the hazards arising in floating dock operations in shipyards.

Chen et al. (2025) presented a decision support system that integrates the Fine Kinney method with SFSs to assess occupational health and safety risks. They presented a decision support system that integrates the Fine–Kinney method with the global fuzzy MABAC method and the Ordered Weighted Average (OWA) operator to assess occupational health and safety risks.

Tatar et al. (2025) developed an innovative approach called Global Fuzzy FUCOM (Full Consistency Method), Fine Kinney, ARTASI (Alternative Ranking Technique based on Adaptive Standardized Intervals) to develop an ergonomic risk assessment tool for workers in seaport operations.

Yakut and Kaya (2025) developed an applied risk model for various sectors in the field of OHS by integrating the SFN and Fine Kinney Methods and combining multi-criteria decision-making methods (TOPSIS, VIKOR, WASPAS, DEMATEL).

Conclusions and Recommendations

The findings examined in this study show that traditional risk assessment methods are insufficient in fully reflecting the uncertainty and indecision of experts. Spherical Fuzzy Numbers (SFN) enable the independent definition of membership, non-membership, and uncertainty values, thereby allowing for a more reliable modeling of uncertainty and subjective judgments in risk assessments. Research shows that integrating SFN with classical risk assessment techniques increases accuracy and reliability, particularly in prioritizing risks in complex industrial environments. Accordingly, adopting SFN-based models in OHS risk management processes enables a more comprehensive assessment that encompasses both technical and human factors. Furthermore, sector-specific model development, training and capacity building for OHS professionals to effectively use these tools, and continuous validation and updating of the models are recommended. Future work is expected to further enhance risk prediction and prioritization capabilities by combining SFS with other advanced SFS types and optimization techniques. In this context, SFS-based risk assessment methods offer decision-makers a more reliable and flexible approach to OHS management.

References

- Özkılıç, Ö. (2005). *İş sağlığı ve güvenliği yönetim sistemleri ve risk değerlendirme metodolojileri* (4. Baskı). Ankara, Türkiye: Ajans-Türk Basın ve Basımevi, ss. 56–72.
- International Organization for Standardization. (2018). *ISO 45001:2018 Occupational health and safety management systems—Requirements with guidance for use*. Geneva, Switzerland: ISO.
- Tixier, J., Dusserre, G., Salvi, O., & Gaston, D. (2002). Review of 62 risk analysis methodologies of industrial plants. *Journal of Loss Prevention in the Process Industries*, 15(4), 291–303.
- Yaylalı, D. (2024). İş güvenliği uzmanlarının risk değerlendirme yöntemi tercihlerine etki eden faktörler. *Karamanoğlu Mehmetbey Üniversitesi Mühendislik ve Doğa Bilimleri Dergisi*, 6(1), 52–65.
- Şimşek, S. (2020). İş sağlığı ve güvenliği kapsamında risk değerlendirme metotlarından Fine Kinney metodunun bir örnekle değerlendirilmesi. *İSG Akademik*, 2(2), 91–99.
- Medeni, B., & İlhan, V. (2024). İş sağlığı ve güvenliği açısından risk değerlendirmesi. B. Medeni & V. İlhan (Ed.), *Sağlık teknikerleri için iş sağlığı ve güvenliği içinde* (ss. 73–84). İstanbul, Türkiye: Nobel Akademik Yayıncılık.
- Ringdahl, L. H. (2004). Relationships between accident investigations, risk analysis and safety management. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 111, 13–19.

Pinto, A., I. L. Nunes, & R. A. Ribeiro. (2011). Occupational risk assessment in construction industry — Overview and reflection. *Safety Science*, 49, 616–624.

Zorluer, İ., & Eleren, A. (2011). İnşaat sektöründe iş güvenliği ve sağlığı üzerine risklerin belirlenmesi ve örnek bir uygulama. *İşçi Sağlığı ve İş Güvenliği Sempozyumu Bildiriler Kitabı* içinde (ss. 185–193). Çorum, Türkiye.

Zadeh, L. A. (1965). Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control*, 8(3), 338–353.

Zadeh, L. A. (1975). The concept of a linguistic variable and its application to approximate reasoning—I. *Information Sciences*, 8(3), 199–249.

Kutlu Gündoğdu, F., & Kahraman, C. (2019). Spherical fuzzy sets and spherical fuzzy TOPSIS method. *Journal of Intelligent & Fuzzy Systems*, 36(1), 337–352.

Gündoğdu, F. K., & Seyfi-Shishavan, S. A. (2021). Occupational risk assessment using spherical fuzzy safety and critical effect analysis for shipyards. *Journal of ETA Maritime Science*, 9(2), 110-119. <https://doi.org/10.4274/jems.2021.59480>

Hacibektasoglu, S. E., Mertoglu, B., & Tozan, H. (2021). Application of a novel hybrid f-SC risk analysis method in the paint industry. *Sustainability*, 13(24), 13605. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132413605>

Kutlu Gündoğdu, F. (2024). Hazard identification and risk assessment for sustainable shipyard floating dock operations: An integrated spherical fuzzy analytical hierarchy process and fuzzy CoCoSo approach. *Sustainability*, 16(13), 5790.

Yılmaz Kaya, B., & Lotfi, R. (2022). Minimizing OHS risks with spherical fuzzy sets as a verdict to inventory management: A case regarding energy companies. *Discrete Dynamics in Nature and Society*, 2022, 1-26. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/9511339>

Wang, Y., Wang, W., Deveci, M., & Yu, X. (2024). An integrated interval-valued spherical fuzzy Choquet integral based decision-making model for prioritizing risk in Fine-Kinney. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence*, 127, 107316.

Bayhun, S., & Demirel, N. Ç. (2024). Hazard identification and risk assessment for sustainable shipyard floating dock operations: An integrated spherical fuzzy analytical hierarchy process and fuzzy CoCoSo approach. *Sustainability*, 16(13), 5790.

Chen, Y., Yu, X., & Yang, Z. (2025). A fuzzy decision support system for risk prioritization in Fine Kinney-based occupational risk analysis. *Journal of Soft Computing and Decision Analytics*, 3(1), 1–17.

Tatar, V., Ayvaz, B., & Pamucar, D. (2025). A quantitative ergonomic risk assessment model of maritime port operations: An integrated spherical fuzzy-FUCOM-ARTASI approach. *Ocean and Coastal Management*, 267, 107542.

Yakut,M., &Kaya,İ.(2025).Bulanık kümeler kapsamında risk analizi yaklaşımlarının değerlendirilmesi ve iş güvenliği kapsamında uygulanması ,Doktora tezi,Yıldız Teknik Üniversitesi,Fen Bilimleri Enstitüsü,İstanbul.